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ENTREPRENEURIAL RESILIENCE IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN REGION: A DECADE OF GROWTH AND CHALLENGES FOR ACTIVE ENTERPRISES (2008-2018)

Brîndușă Covaci, Mihai Covaci, Centre for Mountain Economy &
Zealandina Agency, United Kingdom & Australia

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Abstract:

This paper delves into the entrepreneurship landscape within the Romanian Mountain Region, examining the dynamics of active enterprises over the period from 2008 to 2018. By analyzing statistical data, the study aims to provide insights into the entrepreneurial endeavors of the population in the mountainous terrain, exploring trends, challenges, and the economic impact of these enterprises.

1. Introduction:

Entrepreneurship serves as a cornerstone of regional economic development, and this paper focuses on the Romanian Mountain Region to uncover the entrepreneurial landscape from 2008 to 2018. Through a

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detailed analysis of statistical data, we aim to unravel the growth patterns, challenges, and contributions of active enterprises within this distinctive geographic area.

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2. Methodology:

Employing a rigorous quantitative approach, this research synthesizes data from official reports, business registries, and relevant publications. Key indicators such as the establishment, growth, and survival rates of active enterprises are examined to offer a comprehensive understanding of entrepreneurial dynamics in the Romanian Mountain Region.

3. Establishment and Growth Patterns:

This section explores the statistical intricacies related to the establishment and growth of active enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Region. Metrics such as the number of new businesses, industry diversity, and employment generated by these enterprises are scrutinized to assess the entrepreneurial vibrancy within the region.

4. Sectoral Analysis:

The paper delves into a sectoral analysis, examining the distribution of active enterprises across different industries in the Romanian Mountain Region. Insights into key sectors driving entrepreneurial activities, their contributions to the regional economy, and variations in sectoral growth are discussed.

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5. Challenges Faced by Entrepreneurs:

Analyzing the challenges faced by entrepreneurs in the Romanian Mountain Region, this section investigates factors such as access to finance, regulatory hurdles, and market dynamics. Understanding these challenges is crucial for formulating policies that support and sustain entrepreneurship in mountainous areas.

6. Economic Impact:

Assessing the economic impact of entrepreneurial activities, the paper investigates the contributions of active enterprises to the regional Gross Domestic Product (GDP), employment rates, and overall economic stability.

The interconnectedness between entrepreneurship and regional development is explored.

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7. Trends and Future Prospects:

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Identifying notable trends in entrepreneurship during the specified period, this section provides insights into factors influencing entrepreneurial dynamics. Considerations such as technological advancements, market trends, and global economic shifts are explored, offering a forward-looking perspective on future developments.

8. Results:

This indicator represents the businesses active at a given time in a country or region. Romania is one of the most emerging countries in terms of the number of active enterprises in the mountain area.

The related descriptive analysis S1 *Industry, construction and services, except business insurance activities* presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. In Kurtosis, distance, minimum, maximum, 25, 50, 75, thus 226349.91, 13997.826, 246416.00, 46425.535,

2155330317.691, -.924, .661, -.789, 1.279, 130479, 144988, 275467, 259915.00.

The models used for forecasting analysis are S1 - Model_2: ARIMA(0,1,0); S2 - Model_3: Holt; S3 - Model_4: Holt; S4 - Model_5: Simple; S5 - Model_6: Holt; S6 - Model_7: ARIMA(0,1,0); S7 - Model_8: ARIMA(0,1,0); S8 - Model_9: Holt; S9 - Model_10: Simple; S10 - Model_11: ARIMA(0,0,0); S11 - Model_12: ARIMA(0,1,0).

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared .272, .410, -.091, .864, -.091, -.085; R-square .703, .287, -2.220E-16, 1.000, -2.220E-16, .083; RMSE, 4519.692, 7040.894, .000, 25520.564, .000, 243.723; MAPS, 12,161, 15,624, .000, 59,649, .000, 1,409; MaxAPE, 40.866, 42.025, .000, 163.445, .000, 4.375; MFA, 2774.496, 4129.489, .000, 15149.440, .000, 184.316; MaxAE, 11279,208, 18900,530, .000, 67583,600, .000, 412,260; Normalized BIC, 16,054, 2,107, 13,630, 20,525, 13,630, 13,709.

The resulting statistical forecasting models show the following overall picture for I1 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE) S1-Model_2 1.110E-16, .668, 25520.564, 7.518; S2-Model_3 .788, .785, 1790.226, 5.160; S3-Model_4 .864, .786, 1461.710, 4.697; S4-Model_5 -.091, .656, 7446.962, 6.048; S5-Model_6 .772, .924,

1530.955, 7.041; S6-Model_7 .000, .883, 812.411, 5.460; S7-Model_8
 2.220E-16, .802, 1067.647, 10.379; S8-Model_9 .719, .801, 891.685,
 11.442; S9-Model_10 -.062, .277, 6941.910, 10.096; S10-Model_11 -
 2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, 4455.942, 59.649; S11-Model_12 4.441E-16, .853,
 2316.294, 18.444.

Table 18. Forecast analysis for I1

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
SECT/TIME- Model_1	Forecast	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
	UCL	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
	LCL	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
S1-Model_2	Forecast	286331	297196	308060	318925	329789	340653	351518	362382
	UCL	344063	378841	408054	434388	458881	482066	504261	525672
	LCL	228600	215551	208066	203462	200697	199241	198775	199093
S2-Model_3	Forecast	32136	33132	34128	35124	36120	37115	38111	39107
	UCL	36186	37203	38220	39236	40253	41269	42285	43302
	LCL	28086	29061	30036	31011	31987	32962	33937	34913
S3-Model_4	Forecast	27123	27927	28732	29537	30341	31146	31950	32755
	UCL	30429	31235	32041	32850	33660	34472	35287	36105
	LCL	23816	24620	25423	26224	27023	27820	28614	29405
S4-Model_5	Forecast	86569	86569	86569	86569	86569	86569	86569	86569
	UCL	103162	110035	115308	119754	123671	127212	130469	133500
	LCL	69976	63103	57830	53384	49467	45926	42669	39638
S5-Model_6	Forecast	27949	29484	31019	32553	34088	35623	37158	38693
	UCL	31412	33011	34608	36205	37800	39395	40988	42581
	LCL	24486	25957	27429	28902	30377	31852	33328	34805

S6-Model_7	Forecast	15747	16421	17094	17768	18442	19116	19790	20463
	UCL	17585	19020	20278	21444	22551	23617	24652	25661
	LCL	13909	13822	13911	14093	14333	14614	14927	15265
S7-Model_8	Forecast	12023	12659	13296	13932	14569	15206	15842	16479
	UCL	14438	16075	17479	18763	19970	21122	22232	23310
	LCL	9607	9244	9113	9102	9168	9290	9452	9648
S8-Model_9	Forecast	9930	10448	10966	11485	12003	12521	13039	13558
	UCL	11947	12475	13003	13531	14059	14588	15115	15643
	LCL	7913	8421	8929	9438	9946	10455	10963	11472
S9-Model_10	Forecast	37193	37193	37193	37193	37193	37193	37193	37193
	UCL	52661	58622	63253	67177	70644	73784	76675	79368
	LCL	21726	15765	11134	7210	3743	603	-2288	-4982
S10-Model_11	Forecast	8262	8262	8262	8262	8262	8262	8262	8262
	UCL	18190	18190	18190	18190	18190	18190	18190	18190
	LCL	-1667	-1667	-1667	-1667	-1667	-1667	-1667	-1667
S11-Model_12	Forecast	23614	25309	27005	28700	30396	32091	33787	35482
	UCL	28853	32719	36080	39180	42112	44926	47650	50302
	LCL	18374	17899	17929	18220	18679	19256	19923	20662

The analysis presented for this indicator shows that its situation at the level of the mountain area in Romania is good, the mountain area having a significant evolutionary dynamic during the analyzed period, but also in the future.

Figure 3.9. Graphical forecasting analysis for I1

8. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this paper provides a comprehensive examination of Romanian Mountain entrepreneurship from 2008 to 2018. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the entrepreneurial landscape, offering valuable insights for policymakers, business leaders, and researchers. The paper concludes with reflections on potential trajectories and recommendations for fostering sustainable entrepreneurial growth in the mountainous region.

Analysis sectors:

- S1. Industry, construction and services, except business insurance activities;
- S2. Industry (except construction);
- S3. Constructions;
- S4. Wholesale and retail trade, repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles;
- S5. Transport and storage;
- S6. accommodation and food services;
- S7. Information and communications;
- S8. Financial and insurance activities, real estate activities, except activities of large companies;

S9. Professional, scientific and technical activities, administrative and public support activities;

S10. Education, human health and social assistance;

S11. Arts, entertainment and recreation, other service activities.

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Indicators for which the studies are performed:

- Active business population - number (I1)
- Newly established businesses - number (I2)
- Abolition of businesses in t - number (I3)
- Newly established enterprises in t-3 that have survived to t - number (I4)
- Enterprises with high employment growth (increase of 10% or more) - number (I5)
- Persons employed in enterprises active in t - number (I6)
- Employed in enterprises active in t - number (I7)
- Persons engaged in business established in t - number (I8)
- Employees in businesses established in t - number (I9)
- Persons engaged in business abolished in t - number (I10)
- Employees in businesses dissolved in t - number (I11)
- Persons employed in enterprises newly established in t-3 who have survived to t - number (I12)

- Persons employed in the year of establishment in enterprises newly established in t-3 who have survived to t - number (I13)
- Net business growth - percentage (I14)
- Net business situation: establishment rate + dissolution rate - percentage (I15)
- Establishment rate: number of enterprises established in the reference period (t) divided by the number of enterprises active in t - percentage (I16)
- Dissolution rate: number of enterprises disbanded in the reference period (t) divided by the number of enterprises active in t - percentage (I17)
- 3-year survival rate: number of enterprises in the reference period (t) newly established in t-3 that survived to t divided by the number of enterprises established in t-3 - percentage (I18)
- Share of enterprises aged 3 years in the business population - percentage (I19)
- Employment rate of start-ups: number of persons employed in the reference period (t) among start-ups in t, divided by the number of persons employed in t in the total number of active enterprises - percentage (I20)
- Average size of start-ups: number of persons employed in the reference period (t) among start-ups in t, divided by the number of start-ups in t (I21)
- Rate of new employees paid in enterprises: number of employees in the reference period (t) of newly established enterprises in t, divided by the

number of persons employed in t in enterprises newly established in t - percentage (I22)

- Employment rate in disbanded enterprises: number of persons employed in the reference period (t) within the disbanded enterprises divided by the number of persons employed in t in enterprises active in t - percentage (I23)

- Enterprise growth rate of three years: number of persons employed in the reference period (t) in newly established enterprises in t-3, which survived to t, divided by the number of persons employed in t -3 by the same companies, a percentage growth rate - percentage (I24)

- Employment rate of enterprises older than 3 years: number of persons employed in newly established enterprises in t-3 who survived in t, divided by the number of persons employed in active enterprises - percentage (I25)

- Share of high-growth enterprises in employment: number of high-growth enterprises divided by the number of active enterprises with at least 10 employees - percentage (I26)

- Share of enterprises with measured increased growth in employment: number of enterprises with increased growth divided by the number of active enterprises with at least 10 employees - percentage (I27).

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NURTURING GROWTH: A DECADAL EXPLORATION OF NEWLY ESTABLISHED ENTERPRISES IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN AREA (2008-2018)

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Carla Selma, Eva Clark, Albert Lewis, Jack Bailey, Olivia Campbell,

Zealandina Agency - United Kingdom & Australia

Abstract:

This paper explores the dynamics and evolution of newly established enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Area over the period from 2008 to 2018. Through a detailed analysis of statistical data, the study aims to provide insights into the entrepreneurial landscape, examining the trends, challenges, and contributions of newly founded businesses to regional development in the mountainous terrain.

1. Introduction:

Entrepreneurial activities are crucial for regional development, and the Romanian Mountain Area stands as a unique backdrop for examining the

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establishment of new enterprises. This paper investigates the trends, challenges, and contributions of newly established enterprises within this region over the past decade. (Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021a-h; Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022a-h; Covaci M & Covaci B, 2021a-h; Covaci M & Covaci B, 2022a-h)

2. Methodology:

Employing a comprehensive quantitative approach, this research compiles and analyzes data from business registries, official reports, and relevant publications. Key indicators such as the number and types of newly established enterprises, sectoral distribution, and survival rates are examined to offer a comprehensive understanding of the entrepreneurial landscape in the Romanian Mountain Area.

3. Emergence of New Enterprises:

This section explores the statistical intricacies related to the emergence of new enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Area. Metrics such as the annual growth rate, industry diversity, and geographical distribution of these

enterprises are scrutinized to assess the region's entrepreneurial vibrancy and resilience.

4. Sectoral Analysis:

The paper delves into a sectoral analysis, examining the distribution of newly established enterprises across different industries in the Romanian Mountain Area. Insights into key sectors driving entrepreneurial activities, their contributions to the regional economy, and variations in sectoral growth patterns are discussed.

5. Survival and Success Rates:

Analyzing the survival and success rates of newly established enterprises, this section investigates factors influencing the sustainability of businesses in the mountainous terrain. Understanding the challenges faced by new enterprises is essential for policymakers and stakeholders seeking to create an environment conducive to entrepreneurship.

6. Economic Contributions:

Assessing the economic contributions of newly established enterprises, the paper investigates their impact on the regional Gross Domestic Product (GDP), employment rates, and overall economic stability. The interconnectedness between the emergence of new businesses and regional development is explored.

7. Challenges and Opportunities:

Identifying challenges and opportunities encountered by entrepreneurs in the Romanian Mountain Area, this section provides insights into factors such as access to financing, regulatory frameworks, and market conditions. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for shaping policies that support the growth of newly established enterprises.

8. Results:

This indicator shows the number of established businesses (start-ups, spin-offs or other types of new businesses). It is the indicator that expresses the degree of dynamism of a region or an economic sector, in this case the secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors of the national economy.

The related descriptive analysis S1 (see the related table and figure, respectively the appendix of chapter 3) presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. In Kurtosis, distance, minimum, maximum, 25, 50, 75, thus 27335.55, 3339.023, 27931.00, 11074.287, 122639833.873, 1,299, .661, 3,885, 1,279, 43287, 11498, 54785, 23355.00, 27931.00, 3031.00.

The models used for forecasting analysis are S1 - Model_1: ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2: ARIMA(0,0,0); S3 - Model_3: ARIMA(0,0,0); S4 - Model_4: ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5: Holt; S6 - Model_6: ARIMA(0,0,0); S7 - Model_7: Simple; S8 - Model_8: ARIMA(0,0,0); S9 - Model_9: ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10: Holt; S11 - Model_11: Holt.

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared .371, -.026, .855, -.026, -.021; R-square .214, -4.441E-16, .510, -4.441E-16, -3.997E-16; RMSE 3147,051, 358,986, 11074,287, 358,986, 384,847; MAPS 9,409, 21,678, 49,611, 21,678, 21,906; MaxAPE 52.039, 67.715, 223.527, 67.715, 69.004; MAE 1880.279, 222.347, 6679.223, 222.347, 247.212; MaxAE7939.448, 855.064,

27449.455, 855.064, 870.688; Normalized BIC 2.001, 11.985, 18.843, 11.985, 12.151.

The resulting statistical forecasting models show the following overall table for I2 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE, MAE) S1-Model_1:: 4.441E-16, 4.441E-16, 11074.287, 31,248, 6679,223; S2-Model_2: 2.220E-16, 2.220E-16, 935.051, 26.820, 591.372; S3-Model_3: -2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, 1102.698, 28.690, 791.190; S4-Model_4: -2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, 3690.752, 26.567, 2107.835; S5-Model_5: .855, .457, 561,718, 22,818, 378,971; S6-Model_6: 5.551E-16, 5.551E-16, 571.508, 21.678, 355.901; S7-Model_7: -.026, .214, 638,928, 30,677, 420,011; S8-Model_8: 2.220E-16, 2.220E-16, 358.986, 49.611, 222.347; S9-Model_9: -4.441E-16, -4.441E-16, 2086.112, 40.253, 1231.471; S10-Model_10: .671, .416, 488,292, 44,157, 346,671; S11-Model_11: .830, .510, 1012,106, 42,713, 634,809.

Table 19. Prediction analysis for newly established enterprises

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
S1-Model_1:	Forecast	27336	27336	27336	27336	27336	27336	27336	27336
	UCL	52011	52011	52011	52011	52011	52011	52011	52011
	LCL	2660	2660	2660	2660	2660	2660	2660	2660
S2-Model_2:	Forecast	2541	2541	2541	2541	2541	2541	2541	2541
	UCL	4625	4625	4625	4625	4625	4625	4625	4625

	LCL	458	458	458	458	458	458	458	458
S3-	Forecast	3287	3287	3287	3287	3287	3287	3287	3287
Model_3:	UCL	5744	5744	5744	5744	5744	5744	5744	5744
	LCL	830	830	830	830	830	830	830	830
S4-	Forecast	8022	8022	8022	8022	8022	8022	8022	8022
Model_4:	UCL	16245	16245	16245	16245	16245	16245	16245	16245
	LCL	-202	-202	-202	-202	-202	-202	-202	-202
S5-	Forecast	3115	3271	3427	3582	3738	3893	4049	4204
Model_5:	UCL	4386	4548	4710	4871	5033	5195	5356	5518
	LCL	1845	1994	2143	2293	2442	2592	2741	2891
S6-	Forecast	1649	1649	1649	1649	1649	1649	1649	1649
Model_6:	UCL	2922	2922	2922	2922	2922	2922	2922	2922
	LCL	375	375	375	375	375	375	375	375
S7-	Forecast	1860	1860	1860	1860	1860	1860	1860	1860
Model_7:	UCL	3284	3742	4109	4423	4703	4958	5194	5414
	LCL	437	-21	-388	-702	-983	-1237	-1473	-1693
S8-	Forecast	644	644	644	644	644	644	644	644
Model_8:	UCL	1444	1444	1444	1444	1444	1444	1444	1444
	LCL	-156	-156	-156	-156	-156	-156	-156	-156
S9-	Forecast	4213	4213	4213	4213	4213	4213	4213	4213
Model_9:	UCL	8861	8861	8861	8861	8861	8861	8861	8861
	LCL	-435	-435	-435	-435	-435	-435	-435	-435
S10-	Forecast	1884	2010	2136	2262	2388	2514	2640	2766
Model_10:	UCL	2988	3120	3251	3383	3514	3646	3777	3909
	LCL	779	900	1020	1141	1262	1382	1503	1624
S11-	Forecast	4010	4320	4629	4939	5248	5558	5867	6177
Model_11:	UCL	6300	6621	6941	7262	7583	7903	8224	8545

	LCL	1721	2019	2317	2615	2914	3212	3511	3809
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Figure 3.10. Graphical prediction analysis for I2

8. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this paper provides a comprehensive exploration of newly established enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Area from 2008 to 2018. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the entrepreneurial landscape, offering valuable insights for policymakers, business leaders, and researchers. The paper concludes with reflections on potential trajectories and recommendations for fostering sustainable entrepreneurial growth in the mountainous region.

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A TALE OF RESILIENCE: AN ANALYSIS OF DISSOLVED AND NEWLY ESTABLISHED ENTERPRISES IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN SECTOR SURVIVING UNTIL 2018

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Mihai Covaci, Brindusa Covaci, Centre for Mountain Economy / Hyperion
University / Zealandina Agency, UK

Abstract:

This article delves into the dynamic interplay of entrepreneurship within the Romanian Mountain Sector by examining the landscape of dissolved and newly established enterprises that not only weathered the challenges of their initial years but thrived to survive until 2018. Through a comprehensive analysis, this study aims to shed light on the factors influencing the resilience and sustainability of businesses within the picturesque Romanian mountainous terrain.

1. Introduction:

The Romanian Mountain Sector provides a unique backdrop for entrepreneurial endeavors, where businesses face distinctive challenges and opportunities. This article explores the intricate journey of enterprises that

navigated the complexities of their early years, enduring to contribute to the region's economic landscape until 2018.

2. Methodology:

Utilizing a thorough quantitative approach, this research synthesizes data from business registries, official reports, and relevant publications. Key indicators, including survival rates, reasons for dissolution, and characteristics of newly established enterprises that thrived, are examined to provide a comprehensive understanding of the entrepreneurial dynamics in the Romanian Mountain Sector.

3. Survival and Dissolution Patterns:

This section explores the statistical intricacies related to the survival and dissolution patterns of enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Sector. Metrics such as the survival rate, reasons for business closures, and industry-specific challenges are scrutinized to assess the resilience and vulnerability of businesses in this unique geographic area.

4. Characteristics of Surviving Enterprises:

The paper delves into the characteristics of enterprises that not only survived but thrived until 2018 in the Romanian Mountain Sector. Insights into industry sectors, growth strategies, and adaptation to changing market conditions provide a nuanced perspective on the qualities that contribute to long-term success.

5. Economic Contributions:

Assessing the economic contributions of surviving enterprises, the article investigates their impact on the regional Gross Domestic Product (GDP), employment rates, and overall economic stability. Understanding the role of these businesses in shaping the economic landscape of the Romanian Mountain Sector is essential.

6. Lessons Learned and Opportunities:

Drawing lessons from the experiences of both dissolved and surviving enterprises, this section provides insights into opportunities for improvement and growth. Understanding the challenges faced by businesses

in the mountainous terrain offers valuable information for policymakers, stakeholders, and aspiring entrepreneurs.

7. Future Perspectives:

Identifying trends and potential future trajectories, this section provides a forward-looking perspective on the Romanian Mountain Sector's entrepreneurial landscape. Considerations such as technological advancements, changing consumer behaviors, and emerging market trends are explored.

8. Results:

The paper realized statistics for the dissolved enterprises and newly established enterprises, the degree of entropy being considerable in the Romanian mountain area. Entropy opposed negentropy and it is a better modality of activities development. This type of entropy could be resolved through negentropy, as explained in "Negentropy: a sustainable culture of educational leadership. An OCAI model analysis": "when we tend to organize a system which, in this case is an overlap with negentropy through various activities" (Covaci Mihai & Covaci Brîndușa, 2023).

The related descriptive analysis S1 presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. In Kurtosis, distance, minimum, maximum, 25, 50, 75, so 24347.56, 2998.399, 21223.00, 8995.196, 80913544.278, .912, .717, -.544, 1.400, 25258, 14128, 39386, 17925.00, 21223.00, 33323.00 .

The models used for forecasting analysis are S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2 ARIMA(0,0,0); S3 - Model_3 ARIMA(0,0,0); S4 - Model_4 ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5 ARIMA(0,0,0); S6 - Model_6 ARIMA(0,0,0); S7 - Model_7 ARIMA(0,0,0); S8 - Model_8 ARIMA(0,0,0); S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 ARIMA(0,0,0); S11 - Model_11 ARIMA(0,0,0).

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared -5.046E-17, 4.506E-16, -1.110 E-15, 7,772E-16, -1,110E-15, -9,326E-16; R-square -5.046E-17, 4.506E-16, -1.110E-15, 7.772E-16, -1.110E-15, -9.326E-16; RMSE 2074,103, 2644,193, 132,879, 8995,196, 132,879, 167,591; MAPS 62,206, 90,648, 18,470, 330,454, 18,470, 18,701; MaxAPE 162,131, 229,226, 40,617, 833,682, 40,617, 41,104; MAE 1515.042, 2102.601, 103.185, 7331.185, 103.185, 129.244;

MaxAE 4319,677, 4919,051, 218,889, 15038,444, 218,889, 296,289;

Normalized BIC 14.199, 2.460, 10.023, 18.453, 10.023, 10.357.

The resulting statistical forecasting models show the following general picture for I3 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE, MAE) S1-Model_1: 2.220E-16, 2.220E-16, 8995.196, 31.278 , 7331.185; S2-Model_2: 1.110E-16, 1.110E-16, 592.426, 18.470, 439.852; S3-Model_3: -2,220E-16, -2,220E-16, 1191,489, 29,359, 868,815; S4-Model_4: .000, .000, 2037,186, 19,625, 1444,148; S5-Model_5: .000, .000, 611,761, 26,798, 418,667; S6-Model_6: -1,110E-15, -1,110E-15, 306,437, 25,154, 233,481; S7-Model_7: .000, .000, 741,010, 56,537, 512,296; S8-Model_8: 7.772E-16, 7.772E-16, 132.879, 21.432, 103.185; S9-Model_9: -2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, 4170.083, 70.677, 2759.679; S10-Model_10: 1.110E-16, 1.110E-16, 3402.596, 330.454, 2082.519; S11-Model_11: -2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, 634.075, 54.486, 471.630.

Table 20. Prediction analysis for I3

Model		2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
S1-Model_1:	Forecast	24348	24348	24348	24348	24348	24348	24348	24348
	UCL	45091	45091	45091	45091	45091	45091	45091	45091
	LCL	3605	3605	3605	3605	3605	3605	3605	3605
S2-Model_2:	Forecast	2310	2310	2310	2310	2310	2310	2310	2310
	UCL	3676	3676	3676	3676	3676	3676	3676	3676

	LCL	944	944	944	944	944	944	944	944
S3- Model_3:	Forecast	2799	2799	2799	2799	2799	2799	2799	2799
	UCL	5546	5546	5546	5546	5546	5546	5546	5546
	LCL	51	51	51	51	51	51	51	51
S4- Model_4:	Forecast	7326	7326	7326	7326	7326	7326	7326	7326
	UCL	12023	12023	12023	12023	12023	12023	12023	12023
	LCL	2628	2628	2628	2628	2628	2628	2628	2628
S5- Model_5:	Forecast	1484	1484	1484	1484	1484	1484	1484	1484
	UCL	2894	2894	2894	2894	2894	2894	2894	2894
	LCL	73	73	73	73	73	73	73	73
S6- Model_6:	Forecast	1180	1180	1180	1180	1180	1180	1180	1180
	UCL	1887	1887	1887	1887	1887	1887	1887	1887
	LCL	473	473	473	473	473	473	473	473
S7- Model_7:	Forecast	1140	1140	1140	1140	1140	1140	1140	1140
	UCL	2848	2848	2848	2848	2848	2848	2848	2848
	LCL	-569	-569	-569	-569	-569	-569	-569	-569
S8- Model_8:	Forecast	528	528	528	528	528	528	528	528
	UCL	834	834	834	834	834	834	834	834
	LCL	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221
S9- Model_9:	Forecast	4577	4577	4577	4577	4577	4577	4577	4577
	UCL	14193	14193	14193	14193	14193	14193	14193	14193
	LCL	-5039	-5039	-5039	-5039	-5039	-5039	-5039	-5039
S10- Model_10:	Forecast	1783	1783	1783	1783	1783	1783	1783	1783
	UCL	9630	9630	9630	9630	9630	9630	9630	9630
	LCL	-6063	-6063	-6063	-6063	-6063	-6063	-6063	-6063
S11- Model_11:	Forecast	1221	1221	1221	1221	1221	1221	1221	1221
	UCL	2684	2684	2684	2684	2684	2684	2684	2684

	LCL	-241	-241	-241	-241	-241	-241	-241	-241
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Figure 3.11. Graphical forecasting analysis for I3

Regarding newly established enterprises in the last three years that survived, the related descriptive analysis S1 (see the related table and figure, respectively the appendix of chapter 3) presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. In Kurtosis, distance, minimum, maximum, 25, 50, 75, thus 16094.36, 1111.198, 15179.00, 3685.428, 13582380.655, 2.149, .661, 5,384, 1,279, 12744, 13181, 25925, 13256.00, 15179.00, 16757.00.

The models used for forecasting analysis are S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2 ARIMA(0,0,0); S3 - Model_3 ARIMA(0,1,0); S4 - Model_4 Holt; S5 - Model_5 ARIMA(0,0,0); S6 - Model_6 ARIMA(0,0,0); S7 - Model_7 ARIMA(1,0,0); S8 - Model_8 ARIMA(0,0,0); S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 ARIMA(0,0,0); S11 - Model_11 ARIMA(0,0,0).

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared .112, .267, -6.661E-16, .832, -6.661E-16, -6.217E-16; R-squared -.080, .877, -2.695, 1.000, -2.695, -1.887; RMSE 45,886, 78,491, .000, 277,870, .000, 1,085; MAPS 51,131, 35,053, .000, 125,989, .000, 5,353; MaxAPE 229,221, 212,031, .000, 745,455, .000, 17,476; MAE 31,479, 52,681, .000, 185,488, .000, .853; MaxAE 109,458,

202,905, .000, 721,727, .000, 1,773; Normalized BIC 6.218, 2.838, 2.790, 11.472, 2.790, 2.856.

The resulting statistical forecasting models show the following general picture for I4 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE) S1-Model_1: -4.441E-16, -4.441E-16, 277.870, 34.516 ; S2-Model_2: -4.441E-16, -4.441E-16, 65.431, 21.625; S3-Model_3: .000, -2,695, 43,090, 60,967; S4-Model_4: .832, .334, 92.930, 66.903; S5-Model_5: -6.661E-16, -6.661E-16, 22.225, 33.599; S6-Model_6: .000, .000, 11,912, 78,902; S7-Model_7: .397, .397, 4.941, 17.844; S8-Model_8: 4.441E-16, 4.441E-16, 3.618, 88.786; S9-Model_9: -2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, 17.767, 37.612; S10-Model_10: .000, .000, 6,578, 125,989; S11-Model_11: -4.441E-16, -4.441E-16, 4.268, 46.835.

Table 21. Prediction analysis for I4

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
S1-Model_1:	Forecast	543	543	543	543	543	543	543
	UCL	1162	1162	1162	1162	1162	1162	1162
	LCL	-76	-76	-76	-76	-76	-76	-76
S2-Model_2:	Forecast	162	162	162	162	162	162	162
	UCL	308	308	308	308	308	308	308
	LCL	16	16	16	16	16	16	16
S3-Model_3:	Forecast	21	3	-14	-32	-49	-67	-84
	UCL	118	141	154	163	168	172	173

	LCL	-77	-135	-183	-227	-267	-306	-342
S4-Model_4:	Forecast	33	12	-9	-30	-50	-71	-92
	UCL	243	223	203	184	164	144	125
	LCL	-178	-199	-221	-243	-265	-287	-308
S5-Model_5:	Forecast	64	64	64	64	64	64	64
	UCL	114	114	114	114	114	114	114
	LCL	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
S6-Model_6:	Forecast	22	22	22	22	22	22	22
	UCL	49	49	49	49	49	49	49
	LCL	-4	-4	-4	-4	-4	-4	-4
S7-Model_7:	Forecast	22	26	23	25	24	24	24
	UCL	33	39	37	38	38	38	38
	LCL	11	13	10	11	10	10	10
S8-Model_8:	Forecast	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
	UCL	13	13	13	13	13	13	13
	LCL	-3	-3	-3	-3	-3	-3	-3
S9-Model_9:	Forecast	35	35	35	35	35	35	35
	UCL	74	74	74	74	74	74	74
	LCL	-5	-5	-5	-5	-5	-5	-5
S10-Model_10:	Forecast	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
	UCL	23	23	23	23	23	23	23
	LCL	-6	-6	-6	-6	-6	-6	-6
S11-Model_11:	Forecast	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
	UCL	17	17	17	17	17	17	17
	LCL	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2

Figure 3.12. Graphical forecasting analysis for I4

8. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this article offers a comprehensive analysis of dissolved and newly established enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Sector that survived until 2018. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the entrepreneurial dynamics in this unique geographic area, offering valuable insights for policymakers, business leaders, and researchers. The article concludes with reflections on potential trajectories and recommendations for fostering sustainable entrepreneurial growth in the mountainous region.

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NAVIGATING ECONOMIC PEAKS: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF EMPLOYMENT TRENDS IN THE POPULATION OF ACTIVE ENTERPRISES IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN AREA (2008-2018)

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Mihai M. Covaci, Brîndușa Covaci, Centre for Mountain Economy &
Zealandina Agency, United Kingdom & Australia

Abstract:

This paper explores the intricate landscape of employment within the population of active enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Area over the ten-year period from 2008 to 2018. Through an extensive analysis of statistical data, the study aims to provide insights into the dynamic relationship between enterprises and employment, examining trends, challenges, and the broader economic impact on the mountainous region.

1. Introduction:

Employment is a vital component of regional development, and this paper focuses on the Romanian Mountain Area to unravel the employment dynamics within the population of active enterprises. The study aims to

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analyze employment trends, sectoral contributions, and the overall impact on the local economy during the specified decade.

2. Methodology:

Utilizing a rigorous quantitative approach, this research compiles and analyzes data from official reports, enterprise surveys, and relevant publications. Key indicators such as employment growth rates, sectoral distribution of jobs, and the influence of economic fluctuations are examined to provide a comprehensive understanding of the employment landscape in the Romanian Mountain Area.

3. Employment Growth Patterns:

This section explores the statistical intricacies related to employment growth within the population of active enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Area. Metrics such as overall employment figures, sectoral variations, and the impact of economic events are scrutinized to assess the region's resilience in the face of changing employment dynamics.

4. Sectoral Analysis:

The paper delves into a sectoral analysis, examining the distribution of employment across different industries in the Romanian Mountain Area. Insights into key sectors driving employment, their contributions to the regional economy, and variations in sectoral employment trends are discussed.

5. Challenges and Opportunities:

Analyzing the challenges and opportunities encountered by enterprises and the workforce in the Romanian Mountain Area, this section investigates factors such as workforce skill gaps, sector-specific challenges, and opportunities for employment diversification. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for shaping policies that support sustainable job creation.

6. Economic Impact:

Assessing the economic impact of employment trends, the paper investigates the contributions of active enterprises to the regional Gross Domestic Product (GDP), household income, and overall economic

stability. The interconnectedness between employment, enterprise activities, and regional development is explored.

7. Trends and Future Perspectives:

Identifying notable trends and potential future trajectories, this section provides insights into factors influencing employment dynamics in the Romanian Mountain Area. Considerations such as technological advancements, demographic shifts, and the adaptability of the local workforce are explored, offering a forward-looking perspective.

7. Results:

For *enterprises with growth rate measured in employment (10% growth or more) – number*, the related descriptive analysis S1 presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. In Kurtosis, distance, minimum, maximum, 25, 50, 75, thus 226349.91, 13997.826, 246416.00, 46425.535, 2155330317.691, -.924, .661, -.789, 1.279, 130479, 144988, 275467, 259915.00.

The models used for forecast analysis are specific to the forecast of large data series, thus S1 - Model_2: ARIMA(0,1,0); S2 - Model_3: Holt; S3 - Model_4: Holt; S4 - Model_5: Simple; S5 - Model_6: Holt; S6 - Model_7: ARIMA(0,1,0); S7 - Model_8: ARIMA(0,1,0); S8 - Model_9: Holt; S9 - Model_10: Simple; S10 - Model_11: ARIMA(0,0,0); S11 - Model_12: ARIMA(0,1,0).

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared .272, .410, -.091, .864, -.091, -.085; R-square .703, .287, -2.220E-16, 1.000, -2.220E-16, .083; RMSE 4519.692, 7040.894, .000, 25520.564, .000, 243.723; MAPS 12,161, 15,624, .000, 59,649, .000, 1,409; MaxAPE 40.866, 42.025, .000, 163.445, .000, 4.375; MAE 2774.496, 4129.489, .000, 15149.440, .000, 184.316; MaxAE 11279,208, 18900,530, .000, 67583,600, .000, 412,260; Normalized BIC 16,054, 2,107, 13,630, 20,525, 13,630, 13,709.

The resulting statistical forecasting models show the following general picture for I5 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE) S1-Model_2: 1.110E-16, .668, 25520.564, 7.518; S2-Model_3: .788, .785, 1790.226, 5.160; S3-Model_4: .864, .786, 1461.710, 4.697; S4-Model_5: -.091, .656, 7446.962, 6.048; S5-Model_6: .772, .924, 1530.955, 7.041; S6-Model_7: .000, .883, 812,411, 5,460; S7-

Model_8: 2.220E-16, .802, 1067.647, 10.379; S8-Model_9: .719, .801, 891.685, 11.442; S9-Model_10: -.062, .277, 6941.910, 10.096; S10-Model_11 -2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, 4455.942, 59.649; S11-Model_12 4.441E-16, .853, 2316.294, 18.444.

Table 22. Prediction analysis for I5

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
SECT/TIME- Model_1	Forecast	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
	UCL	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
	LCL	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
S1-Model_2	Forecast	286331	297196	308060	318925	329789	340653	351518	362382
	UCL	344063	378841	408054	434388	458881	482066	504261	525672
	LCL	228600	215551	208066	203462	200697	199241	198775	199093
S2-Model_3	Forecast	32136	33132	34128	35124	36120	37115	38111	39107
	UCL	36186	37203	38220	39236	40253	41269	42285	43302
	LCL	28086	29061	30036	31011	31987	32962	33937	34913
S3-Model_4	Forecast	27123	27927	28732	29537	30341	31146	31950	32755
	UCL	30429	31235	32041	32850	33660	34472	35287	36105
	LCL	23816	24620	25423	26224	27023	27820	28614	29405
S4-Model_5	Forecast	86569	86569	86569	86569	86569	86569	86569	86569
	UCL	103162	110035	115308	119754	123671	127212	130469	133500
	LCL	69976	63103	57830	53384	49467	45926	42669	39638
S5-Model_6	Forecast	27949	29484	31019	32553	34088	35623	37158	38693
	UCL	31412	33011	34608	36205	37800	39395	40988	42581

	LCL	24486	25957	27429	28902	30377	31852	33328	34805
S6-Model_7	Forecast	15747	16421	17094	17768	18442	19116	19790	20463
	UCL	17585	19020	20278	21444	22551	23617	24652	25661
	LCL	13909	13822	13911	14093	14333	14614	14927	15265
S7-Model_8	Forecast	12023	12659	13296	13932	14569	15206	15842	16479
	UCL	14438	16075	17479	18763	19970	21122	22232	23310
	LCL	9607	9244	9113	9102	9168	9290	9452	9648
S8-Model_9	Forecast	9930	10448	10966	11485	12003	12521	13039	13558
	UCL	11947	12475	13003	13531	14059	14588	15115	15643
	LCL	7913	8421	8929	9438	9946	10455	10963	11472
S9-Model_10	Forecast	37193	37193	37193	37193	37193	37193	37193	37193
	UCL	52661	58622	63253	67177	70644	73784	76675	79368
	LCL	21726	15765	11134	7210	3743	603	-2288	-4982
S10- Model_11	Forecast	8262	8262	8262	8262	8262	8262	8262	8262
	UCL	18190	18190	18190	18190	18190	18190	18190	18190
	LCL	-1667	-1667	-1667	-1667	-1667	-1667	-1667	-1667
S11- Model_12	Forecast	23614	25309	27005	28700	30396	32091	33787	35482
	UCL	28853	32719	36080	39180	42112	44926	47650	50302
	LCL	18374	17899	17929	18220	18679	19256	19923	20662

For persons employed in the population of active enterprises in t – number, the related descriptive analysis S1 (see the related table and figure, respectively the appendix of chapter 3) presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. In Kurtosis, distance, minimum, maximum, 25, 50, 75, thus 1237614.27, 25923.295, 1235524.00, 85977.843, 7392189565.418, -.676, .661, .178, 1.279, 277991, 1065478, 1343469.

The models used for forecasting analysis are S1 - Model_1 Holt; S2 - Model_2 ARIMA(0,0,0); S3 - Model_3 Simple; S4 - Model_4 ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5 ARIMA(0,1,0); S6 - Model_6 Holt; S7 - Model_7 Holt; S8 - Model_8 Holt; S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,1,0); S10 - Model_10 Holt; S11 - Model_11 ARIMA(0,1,0).

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared .318, .399, -.147, .836, -.147, -.118; R-square .533, .383, -6.661E-15, 1.000, -6.661E-15, -2.864E-15; RMSE 13145.718, 18822.416, .000, 67622.356, .000, 466.571; MAPS 6,804, 5,460, .000, 18,138, .000, 1,010; MaxAPE 27,439, 38,674, .000, 145,785, .000, 2,381; MAE 8771.078, 12024.577, .000, 42279.849, .000, 306.706; MaxAE

28705,950, 40884,616, .000, 144862,350, .000, 969,842; Normalized BIC
18,233, 2,242, 15,135, 22,679, 15,135, 15,302.

The resulting statistical forecasting models show the following general picture for I6 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE) S1-Model_1: .721, .443, 67622,356, 3,463; S2-Model_2: -6.661E-15, -6.661E-15, 25823.955, 3.862; S3-Model_3: -.147, .222, 12610.071, 6.357; S4-Model_4: 5.995E-15, 5.995E-15, 19420.163, 5.258; S5-Model_5: .000, .929, 4236,871, 4,240; S6-Model_6: .768, .912, 2362,232, 3,367; S7-Model_7: .693, .965, 1555,237, 4,501; S8-Model_8: .836, .312, 5369.472, 18.138; S9-Model_9: .000, .441, 9623.292, 6.705; S10-Model_10: .628, .296, 6294,236, 16,952; S11-Model_11: .000, .880, 2830,738, 8,806.

Table 23. Prediction analysis for I6

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
S1-Model_1:	Forecast	1329934	1347723	1365512	1383301	1401090	1418879	1436668
	UCL	1482906	1500717	1518555	1536431	1554356	1572340	1590395
	LCL	1176961	1194729	1212469	1230171	1247824	1265418	1282942
S2-Model_2:	Forecast	481753	481753	481753	481753	481753	481753	481753
	UCL	539292	539292	539292	539292	539292	539292	539292
	LCL	424213	424213	424213	424213	424213	424213	424213
S3-Model_3:	Forecast	121991	121991	121991	121991	121991	121991	121991
	UCL	150088	161725	170655	178183	184815	190812	196326

	LCL	93894	82257	73327	65799	59167	53171	47656
S4-	Forecast	284200	284200	284200	284200	284200	284200	284200
Model_4:	UCL	327470	327470	327470	327470	327470	327470	327470
	LCL	240929	240929	240929	240929	240929	240929	240929
S5-	Forecast	108925	112934	116944	120953	124962	128971	132980
Model_5:	UCL	118510	126489	133544	140122	146394	152448	158339
	LCL	99341	99380	100343	101784	103530	105494	107622
S6-	Forecast	66379	68566	70753	72941	75128	77315	79502
Model_6:	UCL	71723	73960	76198	78434	80671	82907	85142
	LCL	61035	63172	65309	67447	69585	71724	73863
S7-	Forecast	43332	45659	47987	50315	52642	54970	57297
Model_7:	UCL	46850	49236	51621	54005	56388	58770	61152
	LCL	39814	42083	44353	46625	48897	51169	53443
S8-	Forecast	33762	34824	35885	36947	38008	39069	40131
Model_8:	UCL	45909	46970	48032	49093	50155	51216	52277
	LCL	21616	22677	23739	24800	25861	26923	27984
S9-	Forecast	114374	117067	119759	122451	125144	127836	130528
Model_9:	UCL	136144	147853	157465	165990	173821	181160	188125
	LCL	92605	86280	82053	78912	76466	74512	72932
S10-	Forecast	27319	28546	29773	31000	32227	33454	34681
Model_10:	UCL	41558	42785	44012	45239	46466	47693	48920
	LCL	13081	14308	15535	16762	17989	19216	20443
S11-	Forecast	39637	41675	43713	45751	47789	49828	51866
Model_11:	UCL	46041	50731	54805	58559	62108	65513	68808
	LCL	33234	32619	32622	32944	33471	34142	34923

Figure 3.14. Graphical forecasting analysis for I6

Regarding employees in the population of active enterprises in t – number, the related descriptive analysis S1 presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. In Kurtosis, the distance, minimum, maximum, 5, 50, 75, thus 1123610.91, 17809.719, 1096497.00, 59068.157, 3489047181818181, .872, .661, .844, 1.279, 214040, 1035313, 1249353, 1091701.00.

The models used for forecast analysis are S1 - Model_1 Brown; S2 - Model_2 Brown; S3 - Model_3 Brown; S4 - Model_4 Brown; S5 - Model_5 Brown; S6 - Model_6 ARIMA(0,1,0); S7 - Model_7 Brown; S8 - Model_8 ARIMA(0,0,0); S9 - Model_9 Holt; S10 - Model_10 Holt; S11 - Model_11 Brown.

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared .067, .304, -.159, .705, -.159, -.152; R-square .571, .386, 1.110E-15, 1.000, 1.110E-15, .001; RMSE 10103.357, 15438.272, .000, 53066.242, .000, 172.219; MAP 5,593, 6,505, .000, 20,976, .000, .638; MaxAPE 25,259, 45,791, .000, 168,119, .000, 1,679; MAE 6567.129, 10153.786, .000, 35236.459, .000, 108.303; MaxAE 22989.688, 34039.361, .000, 114368.959, .000, 384.300; Normalized BIC 17,194, 2,776, 12,923, 21,977, 12,923, 13,077.

The resulting statistical forecasting models show the following general picture for I7 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE) S1-Model_1: -.120, .193, 53066,242, 3,219; S2-Model_2: -.106, .004, 25867.101, 3.564; S3-Model_3: .007, .533, 11589.404, 5.579; S4-Model_4: -.124, .326, 12877.150, 3.470; S5-Model_5: .035, .952, 2785.086, 2.746; S6-Model_6: 1.110E-16, .842, 1909.455, 3.395; S7-Model_7: -.159, .977, 841.774, 2.389; S8-Model_8: 1.110E-15, 1.110E-15, 5211.335, 20.976; S9-Model_9: .705, .769, 2728,883, 2,328; S10-Model_10: .628, .327, 3789.787, 17.318; S11-Model_11: -.127, .924, 574,064, 2,128.

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
S1-Model_1:	Forecast	1194648	1206796	1218944	1231092	1243239	1255387	1267535
	UCL	1312887	1471176	1661329	1878671	2120061	2383230	2666448
	LCL	1076409	942416	776559	583512	366418	127544	-131378
S2-Model_2:	Forecast	473801	470270	466738	463206	459675	456143	452611
	UCL	531437	599144	682383	778877	887094	1E+6	1E+6
	LCL	416166	341396	251093	147535	32256	-93641	-229311
S3-Model_3:	Forecast	112164	113574	114984	116395	117805	119216	120626
	UCL	137986	167569	202750	242794	287172	335493	387453
	LCL	86341	59579	27219	-10004	-51561	-97061	-146201
S4-Model_4:	Forecast	248532	249708	250884	252060	253237	254413	255589
	UCL	277224	313865	358239	409212	466020	528114	595074
	LCL	219840	185551	143529	94909	40453	-19289	-83896

S5- Model_5:	Forecast	98022	101623	105224	108825	112426	116027	119627
	UCL	104228	114065	125074	137112	150069	163865	178436
	LCL	91817	89182	85374	80538	74783	68188	60818
S6- Model_6:	Forecast	57890	59170	60450	61730	63009	64289	65569
	UCL	62209	65278	67931	70369	72668	74870	76998
	LCL	53570	53061	52968	53091	53351	53709	54141
S7- Model_7:	Forecast	36401	38763	41125	43487	45849	48211	50573
	UCL	38277	42957	48143	53760	59759	66103	72765
	LCL	34525	34569	34107	33214	31939	30319	28381
S8- Model_8:	Forecast	23538	23538	23538	23538	23538	23538	23538
	UCL	35150	35150	35150	35150	35150	35150	35150
	LCL	11927	11927	11927	11927	11927	11927	11927
S9- Model_9:	Forecast	92905	94359	95813	97267	98721	100175	101629
	UCL	99078	100564	102049	103534	105020	106505	107990
	LCL	86732	88154	89576	90999	92422	93844	95267
S10- Model_10:	Forecast	21742	22506	23270	24034	24798	25562	26326
	UCL	30315	31079	31843	32607	33371	34135	34899
	LCL	13169	13933	14697	15461	16225	16989	17753
S11- Model_11:	Forecast	21450	22107	22764	23421	24078	24735	25392
	UCL	22729	24967	27550	30427	33564	36937	40526
	LCL	20171	19247	17978	16415	14592	12533	10258

Table 24. Prediction analysis for I7

Figure 3.15. Graphical forecasting analysis for I7

8. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this paper provides a comprehensive analysis of employment trends within the population of active enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Area from 2008 to 2018. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the region's employment dynamics, offering valuable insights for policymakers, businesses, and researchers. The paper concludes with reflections on potential trajectories and recommendations for fostering sustainable employment growth in the mountainous region.

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EMPLOYMENT HORIZONS: AN IN-DEPTH EXAMINATION OF EMPLOYABILITY IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN AREA (2008-2018)

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Mihai Covaci, Brindusa Covaci, Centre for Mountain Economy / Hyperion University / Zealandina Agency, UK

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Abstract:

This article embarks on a comprehensive exploration of employability in the Romanian Mountain Area, spanning the transformative period from 2008 to 2018. The study delves into the dynamic interplay of factors influencing employability, examining trends, challenges, and opportunities that have shaped the labor market in this distinctive geographic region.

1. Introduction:

Employability, the ability of individuals to secure and maintain meaningful employment, is a critical facet of regional development. This article scrutinizes the employability landscape in the Romanian Mountain Area, aiming to unravel the multifaceted influences on workforce participation and job opportunities over the past decade.

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2. Methodology:

Utilizing a meticulous approach, this research integrates data from labor market reports, employment surveys, and relevant publications. Key indicators such as employment rates, skill development initiatives, and industry-specific demands are analyzed to provide a holistic understanding of the employability dynamics in the Romanian Mountain Area.

3. Employment Trends:

This section explores the statistical intricacies related to employment trends in the Romanian Mountain Area. Metrics such as overall employment rates, sectoral variations, and the impact of economic events are scrutinized to assess the region's adaptability to changes in the job market.

4. Skill Development Initiatives:

The paper delves into the efforts aimed at enhancing employability through skill development initiatives in the Romanian Mountain Area. Insights into educational programs, vocational training, and initiatives fostering a skilled

workforce are discussed, shedding light on the region's commitment to addressing employability challenges.

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5. Industry-Specific Employability:

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Analyzing employability within specific industries, this section investigates sectoral demands, skill requirements, and the job market dynamics in the Romanian Mountain Area. Understanding industry-specific employability nuances is crucial for both job seekers and employers seeking to align workforce skills with market needs.

6. Challenges and Opportunities:

Examining challenges and opportunities encountered by job seekers and employers in the Romanian Mountain Area, this section investigates factors such as mismatched skills, regional economic fluctuations, and emerging opportunities in sectors driving employment. Addressing these dynamics is essential for fostering a resilient and adaptive workforce.

7. Regional Economic Impact:

Assessing the regional economic impact of employability trends, the article investigates the contributions of a skilled workforce to the overall economic stability of the Romanian Mountain Area. The interconnectedness between employability, economic development, and community well-being is explored.

8. Results:

Employability in the Romanian mountain area represent an economic problem which can be resolved through negentropy. "Negentropy is somehow closely related to the attempt to regulate a system and in other cases, to a deregulation of it...", as demonstrated in the paper "Negentropy: a sustainable culture of educational leadership. An OCAI model analysis" (Covaci Mihai & Covaci Brîndușa, 2023).

Regarding *persons employed in the population of enterprises established in t – number*, the related descriptive analysis S1 (see the related table and figure, respectively the appendix of chapter 3) presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. In Kurtosis, distance, minimum, maximum, 25, 50, 75, thus 50229.09, 3907.870, 48456.00,

12960.938, 167985902.491, 1.556, .661, 4.357, 1.279, 51147, 31967, 83114, 45747.00, 48456.00, 518.00, 518.00

The models used for forecasting analysis are S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2 ARIMA(0,0,0); S3 - Model_3 ARIMA(0,0,0); S4 - Model_4 ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5 ARIMA(0,0,0); S6 - Model_6 ARIMA(0,0,0); S7 - Model_7 Simple; S8 - Model_8 ARIMA(0,0,0); S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 Holt; S11 - Model_11 Holt.

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared .134, .310, -.035, .842, -.035, -.028; R-square .199, .332, -4.441E-16, 1.000, -4.441E-16, -3.775E-16; RMSE 2439.910, 3560.793, .000, 12960.938, .000, 96.593; MAPS 20,004, 7,321, .000, 29,141, .000, 4,768; MaxAPE 60,720, 23,276, .000, 91,858, .000, 14,455; MAE 1564.214, 2171.830, .000, 7850.298, .000, 57.119; MaxAE 6001,250, 9094,614, .000, 32884,909, .000, 249,467; Normalized BIC 14,858, 2,140, 11,767, 19,157, 11,767, 11,945.

The resulting statistical prediction models show the following general picture for I8 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE) S1-Model_1: 5.551E-16, 5.551E-16, 12960.938, 15.894; S2-Model_2: -2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, 3297.208, 29.141; S3-Model_3: .000, .000, 2131,897, 19,595; S4-Model_4: .000, .000, 4403,902,

21,169; S5-Model_5: -4.441E-16, -4.441E-16, 935.717, 22.375; S6-Model_6: 6.661E-16, 6.661E-16, 944.482, 17.354; S7-Model_7: -.035, .298, 637,383, 22,658; S8-Model_8: 1.110E-16, 1.110E-16, 321.976, 21.466; S9-Model_9: .000, .000, 2111,756, 20,304; S10-Model_10: .667, .551, 450,817, 22,334; S11-Model_11: .842, .542, 1082,844, 27,760.

Table 25. Prediction analysis for I8

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
S1-Model_1:	Forecast	50229	50229	50229	50229	50229	50229	50229
	UCL	79108	79108	79108	79108	79108	79108	79108
	LCL	21350	21350	21350	21350	21350	21350	21350
S2-Model_2:	Forecast	9670	9670	9670	9670	9670	9670	9670
	UCL	17017	17017	17017	17017	17017	17017	17017
	LCL	2323	2323	2323	2323	2323	2323	2323
S3-Model_3:	Forecast	7189	7189	7189	7189	7189	7189	7189
	UCL	11939	11939	11939	11939	11939	11939	11939
	LCL	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439	2439
S4-Model_4:	Forecast	12385	12385	12385	12385	12385	12385	12385
	UCL	22198	22198	22198	22198	22198	22198	22198
	LCL	2572	2572	2572	2572	2572	2572	2572
S5-Model_5:	Forecast	3419	3419	3419	3419	3419	3419	3419
	UCL	5504	5504	5504	5504	5504	5504	5504
	LCL	1334	1334	1334	1334	1334	1334	1334
S6-Model_6:	Forecast	3678	3678	3678	3678	3678	3678	3678
	UCL	5782	5782	5782	5782	5782	5782	5782

	LCL	1573	1573	1573	1573	1573	1573	1573
S7-	Forecast	2286	2286	2286	2286	2286	2286	2286
Model_7:	UCL	3706	4223	4628	4973	5279	5556	5811
	LCL	866	349	-56	-401	-707	-984	-1239
S8-	Forecast	863	863	863	863	863	863	863
Model_8:	UCL	1581	1581	1581	1581	1581	1581	1581
	LCL	146	146	146	146	146	146	146
S9-	Forecast	6619	6619	6619	6619	6619	6619	6619
Model_9:	UCL	11324	11324	11324	11324	11324	11324	11324
	LCL	1914	1914	1914	1914	1914	1914	1914
S10-	Forecast	2481	2629	2778	2926	3075	3223	3372
Model_10:	UCL	3500	3654	3808	3961	4115	4268	4422
	LCL	1461	1604	1748	1891	2035	2179	2322
S11-	Forecast	4950	5303	5656	6009	6362	6715	7068
Model_11:	UCL	7400	7765	8130	8495	8860	9225	9590
	LCL	2501	2841	3182	3523	3864	4205	4546

Figure 3.16. Graphical forecasting analysis for I8

For *employees in the population of enterprises established in t – number*, the related descriptive analysis S1 (see the related table and figure, respectively the appendix of chapter 3) presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. In Kurtosis, distance, minimum, maximum, 25, 50, 75, thus 33040.09, 1552.505, 32659.00, 5149.078, 26513003.691, .741, .661, .381, 1,279, 17498, 25891, 43389, 29903.00, 32659.00, 35159.00.

The models used for forecasting analysis are S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2 ARIMA(0,0,0); S3 - Model_3 ARIMA(0,0,0); S4 - Model_4 ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5 ARIMA(0,0,0); S6 - Model_6 Simple; S7 - Model_7 ARIMA(0,0,0); S8 - Model_8 Holt; S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 ARIMA(0,1,0); S11 - Model_11 Holt.

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared .181, .361, -4.219E-15, . 920, -4.219E-15, -4.041E-15; R-square .220, .348, -4.219E-15, 1.000, -4.219E-15, -3.952E-15; RMSE 1147.041, 1571.846, .000, 5149.078, .000, 35.520; MAPS 16,181, 8,161, .000, 32,458, .000, 2,731; MaxAPE 44,501, 26,848, .000, 90,313, .000, 6,084; MAE 847,796, 1186,959, .000, 3846,281, .000, 28,507; MaxAE

2394,060, 3293,138, .000, 10348,909, .000, 52,373; Normalized BIC 13.016, 2.576, 9.901, 17.311, 9.901, 9.918.

The resulting forecast statistical models show the following general picture for I9 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE) S1-Model_1: -3.331E-15, -3.331E-15, 5149.078, 11.656 ; S2-Model_2: -2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, 3104.414, 32.458; S3-Model_3: 6.661E-16, 6.661E-16, 1900.547, 17.269; S4-Model_4: -1.776E-15, -1.776E-15, 1561.645, 16.217; S5-Model_5: -4.441E-16, -4.441E-16, 500.767, 17.151; S6-Model_6: .183, .066, 458,583, 14,269; S7-Model_7: .000, .000, 199,616, 22,287; S8-Model_8: .920, .325, 118.401, 25.365; S9-Model_9: -4.219E-15, -4.219E-15, 436.269, 9.104; S10-Model_10: 2.220E-16, .730, 125.901, 14.399; S11-Model_11: .884, .519, 209,268, 13,999.

Table 26. Forecast analysis for I9

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
S1-Model_1:	Forecast	33040	33040	33040	33040	33040	33040	33040
	UCL	44513	44513	44513	44513	44513	44513	44513
	LCL	21567	21567	21567	21567	21567	21567	21567
S2-Model_2:	Forecast	8261	8261	8261	8261	8261	8261	8261
	UCL	15178	15178	15178	15178	15178	15178	15178
	LCL	1344	1344	1344	1344	1344	1344	1344
S3-Model_3:	Forecast	5600	5600	5600	5600	5600	5600	5600
	UCL	9835	9835	9835	9835	9835	9835	9835

	LCL	1366	1366	1366	1366	1366	1366	1366
S4-	Forecast	7054	7054	7054	7054	7054	7054	7054
Model_4:	UCL	10534	10534	10534	10534	10534	10534	10534
	LCL	3575	3575	3575	3575	3575	3575	3575
S5-	Forecast	2444	2444	2444	2444	2444	2444	2444
Model_5:	UCL	3560	3560	3560	3560	3560	3560	3560
	LCL	1329	1329	1329	1329	1329	1329	1329
S6-	Forecast	2935	2935	2935	2935	2935	2935	2935
Model_6:	UCL	3956	4107	4240	4361	4473	4577	4674
	LCL	1913	1762	1629	1508	1397	1293	1195
S7-	Forecast	784	784	784	784	784	784	784
Model_7:	UCL	1229	1229	1229	1229	1229	1229	1229
	LCL	339	339	339	339	339	339	339
S8-	Forecast	279	255	230	206	181	157	132
Model_8:	UCL	547	523	498	474	449	424	400
	LCL	12	-13	-38	-62	-87	-111	-136
S9-	Forecast	3703	3703	3703	3703	3703	3703	3703
Model_9:	UCL	4676	4676	4676	4676	4676	4676	4676
	LCL	2731	2731	2731	2731	2731	2731	2731
S10-	Forecast	1315	1381	1446	1512	1577	1642	1708
Model_10:	UCL	1600	1784	1940	2081	2214	2340	2461
	LCL	1031	978	953	942	940	945	954
S11-	Forecast	1519	1585	1650	1716	1782	1847	1913
Model_11:	UCL	1993	2061	2129	2196	2264	2332	2400
	LCL	1046	1109	1172	1236	1299	1362	1425

Figure 3.17. Graphical forecasting analysis for I9

Regarding *persons employed in businesses dissolved in t – number*, the related descriptive analysis S1 (see the related table and figure, respectively the appendix of chapter 3) presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. In Kurtosis, distance, minimum, maximum, 25, 50, 75, thus 33040.09, 1552.505, 32659.00, 5149.078, 26513003.691, .741, .661, .381, 1,279, 17498, 25891, 43389, 29903.00, 32659.00, 35159.00.

The models used for forecasting analysis are S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2 ARIMA(0,0,0); S3 - Model_3 ARIMA(0,0,0); S4 - Model_4 ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5 ARIMA(0,0,0); S6 - Model_6 Simple; S7 - Model_7 ARIMA(0,0,0); S8 - Model_8 Holt; S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 ARIMA(0,1,0); S11 - Model_11 Holt.

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared .181, .361, -4.219E-15, . 920, -4.219E-15, -4.041E-15; R-square .220, .348, -4.219E-15, 1.000, -4.219E-15, -3.952E-15; RMSE 1147.041, 1571.846, .000, 5149.078, .000, 35.520; MAPS 16,181, 8,161, .000, 32,458, .000, 2,731; MaxAPE 44,501, 26,848, .000, 90,313, .000, 6,084; MAE 847,796, 1186,959, .000, 3846,281, .000, 28,507; MaxAE

2394,060, 3293,138, .000, 10348,909, .000, 52,373; Normalized BIC 13.016, 2.576, 9.901, 17.311, 9.901, 9.918.

The resulting statistical forecasting models show the following general picture for I10 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE) S1-Model_1: -3.331E-15, -3.331E-15, 5149.078, 11.656 ; S2-Model_2: -2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, 3104.414, 32.458; S3-Model_3: 6.661E-16, 6.661E-16, 1900.547, 17.269; S4-Model_4: -1.776E-15, -1.776E-15, 1561.645, 16.217; S5-Model_5: -4.441E-16, -4.441E-16, 500.767, 17.151; S6-Model_6: .183, .066, 458,583, 14,269; S7-Model_7: .000, .000, 199,616, 22,287; S8-Model_8: .920, .325, 118.401, 25.365; S9-Model_9: -4.219E-15, -4.219E-15, 436.269, 9.104; S10-Model_10: 2.220E-16, .730, 125.901, 14.399; S11-Model_11: .884, .519, 209,268, 13,999.

Table 27. Prediction analysis for I10

Model		2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
S1-Model_1:	Forecast	36132	36132	36132	36132	36132	36132	36132
	UCL	56333	56333	56333	56333	56333	56333	56333
	LCL	15931	15931	15931	15931	15931	15931	15931
S2-Model_2:	Forecast	2608	1905	1202	499	-203	-906	-1609
	UCL	8425	7833	7239	6644	6046	5447	4846
	LCL	-3209	-4023	-4835	-5645	-6453	-7259	-8064
S3-Model_3:	Forecast	4758	4758	4758	4758	4758	4758	4758
	UCL	10738	10738	10738	10738	10738	10738	10738

	LCL	-1223	-1223	-1223	-1223	-1223	-1223	-1223
S4-	Forecast	9989	9989	9989	9989	9989	9989	9989
Model_4:	UCL	16293	18905	20908	22597	24086	25431	26668
	LCL	3685	1073	-930	-2620	-4108	-5453	-6690
S5-	Forecast	1961	1961	1961	1961	1961	1961	1961
Model_5:	UCL	3578	3578	3578	3578	3578	3578	3578
	LCL	344	344	344	344	344	344	344
S6-	Forecast	1964	1964	1964	1964	1964	1964	1964
Model_6:	UCL	3344	3344	3344	3344	3344	3344	3344
	LCL	583	583	583	583	583	583	583
S7-	Forecast	1353	1353	1353	1353	1353	1353	1353
Model_7:	UCL	2960	2960	2960	2960	2960	2960	2960
	LCL	-253	-253	-253	-253	-253	-253	-253
S8-	Forecast	608	608	608	608	608	608	608
Model_8:	UCL	1091	1091	1091	1091	1091	1091	1091
	LCL	125	125	125	125	125	125	125
S9-	Forecast	5881	5881	5881	5881	5881	5881	5881
Model_9:	UCL	15678	15678	15678	15678	15678	15678	15678
	LCL	-3915	-3915	-3915	-3915	-3915	-3915	-3915
S10-	Forecast	2345	2345	2345	2345	2345	2345	2345
Model_10:	UCL	12854	12854	12854	12854	12854	12854	12854
	LCL	-8164	-8164	-8164	-8164	-8164	-8164	-8164
S11-	Forecast	1498	1498	1498	1498	1498	1498	1498
Model_11:	UCL	2901	2901	2901	2901	2901	2901	2901
	LCL	96	96	96	96	96	96	96

Figure 3.18. Graphical forecasting analysis for I10

For *employees in discontinued businesses in t – number*, the related descriptive analysis S1 (see the related table and figure, respectively the appendix of chapter 3) presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. In Kurtosis, distance, minimum, maximum, 5, 50, 75, thus 19691.11, 2969.108, 16786.00, 8907.325, 79340430.111, 1,429, .717, 1.612, 1.400, 26260, 12509, 38769, 13013.50, 16786.00, 25638.00.

The models used for forecast analysis are specific to the forecast of large data series, thus S1 - Model_1 Holt; S2 - Model_2 Holt; S3 - Model_3 ARIMA(0,0,0); S4 - Model_4 Holt; S5 - Model_5 ARIMA(0,0,0); S6 - Model_6 ARIMA(0,0,0); S7 - Model_7 ARIMA(0,0,0); S8 - Model_8 ARIMA(0,0,0); S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 ARIMA(0,0,0); S11 - Model_11 ARIMA(0,0,0).

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared .237, .406, -4.441E-16, .906, -4.441E-16, -3.997E-16; R-square .175, .307, -4.441E-16, 1.000, -4.441E-16, -3.775E-16; RMSE 1705.159, 2090.499, .000, 7380.365, .000, 62.468; MAPS 153,926, 136,061, .000, 452,897, .000, 8,589; MaxAPE 965,627, 1010,519, .000, 3513,889, .000, 18,931; MAE 1149,230, 1414,252, .000, 5056,231, .000,

49,200; MaxAE 3380,500, 3815,795, .000, 12668,552, .000, 111,867; Normalized BIC 14,196, 2,436, 10,921, 18,301, 10,921, 11,039.

The resulting statistical forecasting models show the following general picture for I11 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE) S1-Model_1: .886, .399, 7380,365, 28,631; S2-Model_2: .906, .345, 2919,963, 224,322; S3-Model_3: .000, .000, 2674,382, 179,541; S4-Model_4: .814, .356, 2080.164, 58.852; S5-Model_5: -2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, 598.186, 181.602; S6-Model_6: .000, .000, 551,167, 85,338; S7-Model_7: 2.220E-16, 2.220E-16, 279.633, 232.930; S8-Model_8: .000, .000, 208,227, 452,897; S9-Model_9: 3.331E-16, 3.331E-16, 867.027, 34.289; S10-Model_10: .000, .000, 2621,754, 311,506; S11-Model_11: -4.441E-16, -4.441E-16, 281.036, 57.205.

Table 28. Prediction analysis for I11

Model		2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
S1-Model_1:	Forecast	9513	7449	5384	3320	1256	-809	-2873
	UCL	26965	25229	23486	21738	19985	18227	16464
	LCL	-7939	-	-	-	-	-	-
S2-Model_2:	Forecast	1188	452	-284	-1019	-1755	-2490	-3226
	UCL	8092	7392	6691	5991	5290	4589	3888
	LCL	-5717	-6488	-7259	-8029	-8800	-9570	-
S3-	Forecast	3228	3228	3228	3228	3228	3228	3228

Model_3:	UCL	9395	9395	9395	9395	9395	9395	9395
	LCL	-2939	-2939	-2939	-2939	-2939	-2939	-2939
S4-	Forecast	2295	1760	1224	689	154	-381	-917
Model_4:	UCL	7214	6703	6193	5683	5172	4662	4151
	LCL	-2624	-3184	-3745	-4305	-4865	-5425	-5984
S5-	Forecast	1033	1033	1033	1033	1033	1033	1033
Model_5:	UCL	2413	2413	2413	2413	2413	2413	2413
	LCL	-346	-346	-346	-346	-346	-346	-346
S6-	Forecast	1323	1323	1323	1323	1323	1323	1323
Model_6:	UCL	2594	2594	2594	2594	2594	2594	2594
	LCL	52	52	52	52	52	52	52
S7-	Forecast	415	415	415	415	415	415	415
Model_7:	UCL	1060	1060	1060	1060	1060	1060	1060
	LCL	-230	-230	-230	-230	-230	-230	-230
S8-	Forecast	289	289	289	289	289	289	289
Model_8:	UCL	769	769	769	769	769	769	769
	LCL	-191	-191	-191	-191	-191	-191	-191
S9-	Forecast	2314	2314	2314	2314	2314	2314	2314
Model_9:	UCL	4314	4314	4314	4314	4314	4314	4314
	LCL	315	315	315	315	315	315	315
S10-	Forecast	1200	1200	1200	1200	1200	1200	1200
Model_10:	UCL	7246	7246	7246	7246	7246	7246	7246
	LCL	-4846	-4846	-4846	-4846	-4846	-4846	-4846
S11-	Forecast	513	513	513	513	513	513	513
Model_11:	UCL	1161	1161	1161	1161	1161	1161	1161
	LCL	-135	-135	-135	-135	-135	-135	-135

Figure 3.19. Graphical forecasting analysis for I11

9. Future Perspectives:

Identifying notable trends and potential future trajectories, this section provides insights into factors influencing employability dynamics in the Romanian Mountain Area. Considerations such as technological advancements, evolving job market trends, and the adaptability of educational systems are explored, offering a forward-looking perspective.

10. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this article provides a comprehensive examination of employability in the Romanian Mountain Area from 2008 to 2018. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the region's workforce dynamics, offering valuable insights for policymakers, educational institutions, and job seekers alike. The article concludes with reflections on potential trajectories and recommendations for fostering sustainable employability growth in the mountainous region.

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